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The peculiarities of the online public access catalogue in the art library

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Abstract:

Online public access catalogue in the Russian State Art Library, Moscow (RSAL), which was founded as theatrical library, has some peculiarities because of both the specifics of its collections and specifics of its readers requests. To fulfil the readers requests, RSAL developed the methodology of subject description and provided the search abilities in the online catalogue, including search with the use of the authority file.

This paper describes some aspects of this methodology, explains what decisions on approach to subject description were made in RSAL and why. Problems that are covered in this paper include unified search, wide and narrow subject headings, subject search on pictorial materials database, authority file and document preservation passport. The methodology is illustrated with several examples.

Keywords: art Library, OPAC, cataloguing, subject headings, authority file.

The Russian State Art Library was founded in 1922 as theatrical library, and until 1992 it was named the Central State Theatre Library. The users of the RSAL are directors, actors, architects, designers, art critics and art historians, theatre and cinema artists, sculptors, etc. The content of the collection and the search engine are oriented to the specialized services to readers. This search is available online via the public online catalogue.

Online public access catalogue (OPAC) is developed in RUSMARC format – Russian version of the international MARC format. It consists of several bibliographical databases:

- books,
- serial publications,
- periodicals (printed and electronic publications),
- video library,
- microfiches,

- catalogue of the pictorial documents collection (engravings, photographs, art postcards, art reproduction, invitation cards, menu, fashion pictures),
- newspaper clippings and theater programs (especially valuable are ones from the end of 19th century and first half of 20th century).

Some documents are digitized and their full texts are available online.

The peculiarities of the electronic catalogue in art library are manifested in bibliographic description and subject indexing.

The Russian State Art Library electronic catalogue provides unified subject search for the documents of different type, allowing both wide and narrowed subject headings, and provides subject search by the annotated graphic material bibliographic entry. The electronic catalogue employs the authority file with the various connections between the headings. In addition, the electronic catalogue includes document preservation passport. The last, but not least, electronic catalogue provides online access to the library collection.

The RSAL adopted unified guidelines to the subject indexing of the documents of different types. The specificities are in the depth of the document content representation: for example, there are more details in the single-page document subject headings.

The search in electronic catalogue is possible on all bibliographic description fields, including annotation and subject headings. The example of this is given on the fig. 1. The search tools on the RSAL main page [1] allow the search in all collections. The search statistics is available to the user, and, based on it, the user can narrow the search results if needed. For example, it is possible to search only documents in the specific language, to limit search to the specific publication date period or to the specific document type. Another possibility is to choose advanced search to browse the electronic catalog subject headings. The existence of the electronic version of the document is marked in search results as "linked entries".

Figure 1. Search options in the RSAL

Even in the subject library such as art library different readers could have very different requests. Some of them need information on a very broad topic, say "Arts theory", and we call such topics "wide". Others are interested in deep research of a specific topic, like "golden ratio in the Renaissance architecture", and such topics are called "narrow".

In case of the subject library, readers are mostly interested in subject search. There are the two reasons for that. First, in the art library the search for narrow topic is more efficient and timesaving because there are specific headings in the catalogue. Second, the reader can get the detailed information on the topic interesting him by browsing through the detailed catalogue.

The comparison of the subject description of the same book in the United States Library of Congress and in the Russian State Art Library shows the difference of the readers' requests and their fulfillment between sectoral and universal library. The first example is the book "A history of German theatre" [2], which is the collected articles on more than 400 pages. In the Library of Congress the content of the book is described in only one subject heading: *Theater--Germany--History*. The twelve subject headings from the Russian State Art Library catalogue are shown in the table 1.

Table 1. Subject description of the book "A history of German theatre"

Original headings (in Russian)	English translation
Кригенбург, Андреас (1963)	Andreas Kriegenburg (1963), stage director
Берлинский театральный фестиваль (44; Германия; 2007)	The Berliner Theatertreffen--(44; Германия; 2007)
Брехт Брехт (1898–1956)--Драматургия	Brecht, Bertolt (1898–1956)--Drama
Чехов, А. П. (1860–1904)--"Три сестры"--Постановки за рубежом--Германия	Chekhov Anton (1860–1904)--"Three sisters", theatre productions outside the Russia--In Germany
"Три сестры", драматический спектакль (2006; "Каммершпиле", театр; Мюнхен, город; Германия)	"Three sisters"--Performance (2006; Münchner Kammerspiele)
Театр немецкий--История--10–21 вв.	Theatre--Germany--10-21 th cent.
Драматургия немецкая--История--13–нач. 21 вв.	German drama--History--13-21 th cent.
Режиссура театра--История--Германия	Theatre--Production and direction--History--Germany
Театр и политика--Германия--20 в	Theatre and politics--Germany--20 th cent.
Театр и идеология--Германия--19–20 вв.	Theatre and ideology--Germany--19–20 th cent.
Театры--Архитектура--Германия--19–20 вв.	Theatre-Architecture-Germany-19–20 th cent.
Сценография немецкая--20 в.	Scenography Germany--20 th cent.

For our readers it is important to represent all these topics in the electronic catalogue headings.

Another example of the book present in both libraries is "Chekhov on the British stage" [3]. In the Library of Congress, it is described somewhat more detailed with three headings:

- Chekhov, Anton Pavlovich, 1860-1904--Stage history--Great Britain
- Chekhov, Anton Pavlovich, 1860-1904--Translations into English--History and criticism
- Theater--Great Britain--History--20th century.

In addition to these subject headings, the RSAL has the following categories of subject headings:

- Personalities (directors, writers)
- The Anton Chekhov's influence on the foreign theatres
- The theater tours and their chronology
- The history of selected productions
- The scenography

The international requirement to the subject indexing is that subject heading shall adequately represent the document content. However, the amount of detail is determined by the library.

The Russian state art library has accumulated a lot of experience in subject indexing. This is because the card subject catalog with more than 500 000 cards was developed from the 1930s to the 1990s in then the Theatrical library. The subject headings on these cards are very detailed. Even now, this subject catalog in digitized form is widely used by readers. The image-based version of this unique subject catalogue is available online.

During the subject indexing, the RSAL catalogers pay attention to the aspects of art theory and art history, art form and genre, styles and art directions, connections and relationships in the art of different nations; titles of shows, movies and art objects. Some other aspects are:

- Technique, technology, and restoration. The example of that subject is *Velázquez, Diego, 1599-1660.--Philip IV hunting Wild Boar--Restoration.*
- Themes, images, plots and iconography. The example of that subject is *Christian iconography--Assumption of Mary—Italy--18 cent.--Collection of articles.*

The important aspect is the problems of creative interpretation of classical and contemporary heritage. One example of how it could be covered in the catalogue is shown below in three subject headings:

- Cohen, F.A. (1904-1967) --"The Green table"--Productions
- Blum, O.--"The Green table", ballet—Productions--Reconstructions in 1980-th
- "The Green table", ballet--History of productions in 1932–1990th.

If describing the document about personality it is mandatory to specify context in the subject subheadings, interviews or memoirs of contemporaries. Yet another important aspect is the formal signs of publication, including not only ordinary catalogs, but also exhibition catalogs, catalog-price lists for the collectors.

The large part of the RSAL collection are the rare and valuable documents of the museum level. The requirements to the description set by thee museums differ from the requirements set by the libraries. In the RSAL description rules both type of

requirements are merged in the scientific description methodology. Below is the data required to create the bibliographical entry:

- Title
- Author: artist, photographer, sculptor, etc.
- Place of production, publishing house, typography, publishing date
- Technique; dimensions.
- Serial number
- Description of particular copy properties: marks, stamps, stickers, etc.
- Copy condition.
- Registration number.
- Reference literature
- Annotation to the image (image description, iconography peculiarities, historical information about the object depicted).

It is worth note that all of the above fields are searchable.

The following rules for the pictorial collection entry description are adopted in the RSAL for the purpose of the description unification.

- Single portrait description shall reflect the following aspects of the image: chest image, waist image or full-length image; turn of the head, torso; full face, in profile (right, left), or in three quarters left or right; staying or sitting, glasses; costume, insignia, awards image background, surrounding landscape, various objects (if any).
- Group portrait description shall describe all persons depicted from left to right, from bottom row to top, staying of sitting, and also costumes (especially details of costumes).
- Event-plot image description shall include most interesting objects starting from the main one and from general to specific.
- Architecture object description shall include object title. If only the part of the object is depicted, the title of the main object precedes the name of the part.
- Scene from the theater performance image description shall include the name of the performance, scene.

The subject description of the image of non-preserved building of the church of 17th century, shown on fig. 2, gives the example of the above rules application. The bibliographic description of this image (photograph taken in the 1st decade of 20th century) includes the following:

- Silver print; 14x9 cm.
- Vertical image. – Stamps on the backside: M-45, 0-10.
- The hipped bell tower on the left, the five-domed church on the right.

Then there are the following subject headings:

- Architecture--Suzdal, city (Vladimir region), 17th cent.--Postcards
- Churches and cathedrals--Suzdal, city (Vladimir region), 17th cent.--Postcards
- Bell towers--hipped roof style--Architecture--Suzdal, city (Vladimir region)--17th cent.--Postcards
- Non-preserved buildings and structures--Suzdal, city (Vladimir region), 17th cent.--Postcards

Figure 2. Postcard with Suzdal Trinity Cathedral (1900s).

The special interest is the photographs that document the historical period. They are very important for directors, artists, and they are the base for movies and spectacles devoted to the specific the historical period.

The two photographs shown on fig. 3 and fig. 4 are from Moscow during the World War II. There are the very detailed subject headings, which are rarely used for book indexing. On the first of them the choreographic class is depicted, and the years is specified in subject headings:

- Choreographic school students--Kids--Costume-USSR--1st Half of 1940s--Photographs
- Choreographic classes--Interiors--USSR--1st Half of 1940s--Photographs

In the annotation of the other photograph the following is specified: open air group portrait of choreographic teachers in the schoolyard (Pushchnaya str., 6). Figures depicted above the hip, full-face, staying, in coats with their head covered, with purses in hands. In the subject headings of the other photograph one can find not only персоналии, изображенные на фотографии, но и предметное описание одежды. The outwear from the first half on the 1940s, but the more detailed fur outwear:

- Group portrait--USSR--1st Half of 1940s--Photographs
- Women's outwear--USSR--1st Half of 1940s--Photographs
- Women's Headdress--USSR--1st Half of 1940s--Photographs
- Fur-Women's outwear--USSR--1st Half of 1940s--Photographs
- Ballet teacher--USSR--1st Half of 1940s--Photographs

Figure 3. Choreographic class (1940s)

Figure 4. Group portrait of the USSR people (1940s)

The subject indexing of all document types in the RSAL is done by the unified rules. So this facilitates the search and correction of the catalog if needed, and also provides more possibilities for replenishment of the authority file.

We create the subject classification database. For this purpose we created the authority file containing the subject collection structure. During the subject indexing the cataloger links one or several subject heading to the document. If there is no suitable heading exists in the authority file, the cataloger creates new heading and incorporate in to the structure on the authority file.

The authority file contains various types of connections between the subject headings. Some headings are related to the different classifications, different branches and it is important that the reader will be able to see and feel the difference. For example, temples as an architecture object or as a worship place. In the first case, it belongs to the Arts section, in the other – to the Religion.

The language of the subject headings should correspond with the scientific language (the terminology of the universal libraries are not always accurate, as it not take into account the specifics, especially in the humanitarian sciences).

The example of the above in the field of periodization: there can be no unifying heading on Renaissance art or North Renaissance art. Because each is a cultural phenomenon with not only local features, it is not enough to use only dates linked to the art of one country.

Authority file is the database that is open to readers. It allows the search not only by separated headings, but also by the headings linked to each other. This structure resembles the navigator on knowledge base for specific sector (art history, theater studies, musicology etc.).

The connections between the person and the activity type, the person and the art works are represented in the authority file. For example (see fig. 5), the link from the subject heading *Chekhov--Dramas--Screen adaptations* leads to the subject heading *Andrei Konchalovsky (1937)*. During the work, the cataloger adds the corresponding entry to the field.

Figure 5. Subject heading for Anton Chekhov dramas screen adaptation

The Russian State Art Library has the database of document preservation passports, containing the data of the preservation state of the books, postcards, photographs and other paper art. The format of the database entries is combined with the bibliographical entries in RUSMARC in OPAC-global.

There is a field (code 318) for the document preservation passport in which the condition of the document is described, including the types of damage. There is a

special interface to work with the passport. The search for specific types of damage is possible. The statistics on the damages and report creation is supported.

The example of the preservation passport is given below. The three-digit number is the field code.

- 309 Binding type: one-piece
- 309 Binding edge: simple
- 309 Endpaper material: cloth
- 316 Features of creation: with original engraving on the title page
- 316 Information recording material: black printing ink
- 316 Information recording material: red printing ink
- 317 Ex-libris (label): libraries "Bibliothek Schloss Plathe Pommern" in the form of the coat of arms with a dragon in a rectangular frame (90x62) on the flyleaf
- 317 Ex-libris (label): territorial region of Germany "Ex libris Schloss – Plathe Pommern" on the endpaper in a rectangular frame (20x90)
- 317 Marks (notes): unidentified person (authograph) on the endpaper and the title page (black ink) \$5PГБИ\$9015399
- 318 Defect – Defect type – Mechanical – Deformation
- 318 Defect – Defect type – Mechanical – Creases
- 318 Defect – Defect type – Biological – Pigmentation
- 318 Defect – Defect type – Sheets drop out – Book block

In conclusion it has to be said that the readers requests change with time, as well as search technologies. The art theory and history is also a living organism. So no methodology and no search system could be fixed and stay unchanging forever. The Russian State Art Library plans the further development of the authority file and the improvement of the electronic catalog search.

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